

THE NATURE OF TRANSLATION TRANSFORMATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Though many linguists addressed and did research about transformation in translation, there is no consensus among scientists regarding the very concept of translation transformation. This article deals with the problems which translators face during their interpreting and translating. We discuss the methods and strategies used by well-known scholars for linguistic transformations and try to explain made mistakes while translating from one language into another one.

Key words: *translation, transformation, technique, strategy, translator, source language, translated text, content, recipient, equivalence.*

INTRODUCTION. The use of translation transformations is by no means a mechanical process, but requires a certain creative effort. This translation technique is a very effective tool for solving the difficulties associated with achieving translation equivalence in the absence of the possibility of translation along linguistic parallels. Therefore, the solution of problems associated with translation transformations seems to us relevant for the theory and practice of translation. Appropriate use of translation transformations in appropriate places is aimed at keeping the translation content as complete as possible, an important issue for translation studies. The complete preservation of the translation content ensures its alternativeness and, ultimately, its high quality. It should be noted that the formal application of translation transformations cannot fully ensure the quality of translation. There are four main approaches to translation. They include linguistic, cultural, pragmatic and sociolinguistic approaches. In the process of translation, these can be theoretically separated. However, in practice, they cannot be separated from each other, because they require each other and serve to complement each other. In fact, based on the above-mentioned approaches, taking into account their principles determine the extralinguistic factors of the translation and ensures the adequacy of the translation.

METHODS. Many well-known translators have more or less addressed to the issue of translation transformations in particular: L.S. Barkhudarov, V.G. Gak, O. Kade, V.N. Komissarov, L K. Latyshev, Ya.I. Retzker, A.D. Schweizer. However,

despite the existence of extensive literature on the problem of translation transformations, there is no consensus among scientists regarding the very concept of translation transformation. Most definitions do not fully reveal the essence of the translation phenomenon under consideration. And in some cases (in the works of V.N. Komissarov, Ya.I. Retsker, G.M. Strelkovskiy and others), the term "translational transformation" is used without a clear definition at all (as an intuitive term). Despite the existence of an extensive literature on the problems of translation, the status of one of the main translation techniques has not yet been determined.

Such a divergence of views in the interpretation of the term "translational transformation" necessitates a detailed consideration of this issue and clarification in understanding the essence of transformations.

The term "transformation" is widely used. We meet him in the works of many translation scholars: A.D. Schweitzer, L.S. Barkhudarova, L.K., Latysheva, I. I. Retsker, R.K., Minyar-Belorucheva, V.N. Komissarov and others. However, we often find interpretations that do not sufficiently reveal the essence of this phenomenon. Scientists from different positions approach the concept of "transformation".

L.S. Barkhudarov proceeds from the fact that translation transformations are those numerous and qualitatively diverse transformations that are carried out to achieve translation equivalence ("translation adequacy") despite the differences in the formal and semantic systems of two languages [1]. A.D. Schweitzer calls translation transformations "interlingual operations of "reexpression" of meaning". V.G. Gak and after him N.K. Garbovsky understand translational transformation as a departure "from the use of isomorphic means available in both languages" [2]. R.K. Minyar-Beloruchev, calling transformation "the basis of most translation techniques", believes that it "consists in changing the formal (lexical and grammatical transformations) or semantic (semantic transformations) components of the source text while maintaining the information intended for transmission".

RESULTS. As we can see, there is no unity in the interpretation of the term "translational transformation". However, it seems important to emphasize that most authors define translation transformations as interlingual transformations that are carried out in order to achieve translation equivalence. Some translation scholars (Barkhudarov L.S., Retsker Ya.I.) also approach the issue of the complex, complex nature of transformations, emphasizing the conventionality of the classifications of translation transformations they propose, which is associated with the complexity of studying this translation technique. It should also be noted that in a number of works the term "transformation" is used without a clear definition (as an intuitive term) (works by V.N. Komissarov, Ya.I. Retsker, G.M. Strelkovsky and others). Let's try to

understand this complex issue and determine what is the essence of such a concept as translation transformation.

The concept of transformation is "borrowed" from the field of monolingual transformations. When we talk about monolingual transformations, we mean phrases that, differing from each other in form (grammatical structure, lexical content, etc.), have practically the same content and are capable of performing one and the same thing in a given context the same communication function.

After analyzing various approaches to solving the problem of the essence of translation transformations, we share the point of view of L.K. Latyshev, who made a significant contribution to the development of a typology of translation transformations, who defines translation transformation as "a method of translation, which is characterized by a departure from the semantic-structural parallelism between the original and translation" [3]. At the same time, it seems important to emphasize that the author of the above concept is the only one who not only touches on the issue of the complex nature of translation interlingual transformations, but for the first time introduces the concept of "mixed transformation", which is associated with the fact that transformations of a mixed type (lexico-syntactic, syntactic-morphological, etc.) [4]. Such an understanding of the nature of translation transformations is, in our opinion, the most adequate translation reality. However, the definition of translation transformation as a deviation from the semantic-structural parallelism between ST and TL leaves open the question of those cases when a translator in the process of bilingual communication with translation encounters a complete absence of linguistic parallels between SL and TL.

DISCUSSION. Literary translation is a process in which the translator is given greater opportunities than the scientific-technical translator. The main reason for this is that the text of the literary translation is the original and to give the reader aesthetic pleasure in the process of reading the translated text. In affecting emotions, the writer or poet uses various art forms, exaggerated, artistically colored words. The translator uses various translation transformations to translate such specific processes encountered in works of art. It is difficult to imagine the translation process without translation transformations, because the most important and highest goal of translation is to achieve adequacy. The task of the translator is to use various translation transformations productively and in the appropriate place, to give the content of the original text as fully as possible in the translated text based on all the features of the language, style, and genre in it. Lexical transformations are used when there is a discrepancy in the lexical meaning of words. The main reason for the use of lexical transformations in most cases is the result of the inconsistency of the meaning of the

word units in the two languages, because the word used in the original language can have one, two, and many meanings, and in the translated language, the meaning of the lexical unit can include a word with only one meaning. Or, on the contrary, the word in the original text and in the translated language may have the same meaning. This opens the way for literal translation. Lexical transformations are applied when the style and use of word meanings and the features of word formation do not match. Grammatical transformation involves making changes in sentence structures in accordance with the norms of the translation language during the translation process. Grammatical transformation involves making changes in sentence structures in accordance with the norms of the translation language during the translation process. Morphological transformations change almost nothing in the content of the text. The syntactic changes made have very little effect on the content of the original text. Syntactic transformations mean changing the syntactic function of a word or phrase. Changing the syntactic function of words and word units requires grammatical transformation, i.e. replacing syntactic constructions. In this case, in most cases, the passive participle is intended to be converted into the personal participle, and vice versa. Semantic transformation is carried out on the basis of the existing various cause and effect relationships between the elements describing the situation. It should be mentioned that translation transformations are rarely found in pure form in translation. they usually come in a mix. This indicates that translation transformations are used as a whole system. Meanwhile, translation transformations consist of the step-by-step combination of complex changes made in the target language. Semantic transformations differ from other transformations in that they have a greater impact on content. A comparison of English and Uzbek languages shows that these phenomena in each language do not correspond to each other. By phonetic transformation we mean transcription and transliteration used in translation. Transcription and transliteration refers to the transcription or transliteration of famous nouns (names), geographical names, names of organizations, offices, institutions, and names of ships and hotels, that is, giving the sounds in the above-mentioned names with appropriate sounds or letters in the translated language.

It is known that in English there are 44 sounds that can be transcribed and transliterated, 20 of which are vowels and 24 are consonants, and 26 letters for transliteration (of which 20 are consonants and 6 are vowels). An example of this is from parallel texts: Shayboniyxon poygada bir-biridan o‘zim, sor burgutday uchib borayotgan yigitlarga zavq bilan tikildi-yu, o‘zi dedi, “Mayli, Bobur kuzdagi g‘alabasidan faxrlanib, qiziga Faxriniso deb ot qo‘ysin, kerilib, she‘rini yozib yotaversin!” (P. Qodirov. Yulduzli tunlar). Shaybani Khan watching his horseman like

golden eagles enthusiastically and censoriously thought: “Babur has become proud. Well, let him feast his eyes upon the autumn victory, let him compose poems, let Fakhrinisso be Fakhrinisso!” (P. Qodirov. Starry nights Babur) In this translation, Shaibaniykhon is a noun, the y is dropped in the translation, and it is separated from the word structure in the form of khan - Khan. Quadratli, katta daryo ham go‘yo uyquga cho‘mgan singari to‘lqinlanmasdan tinch turar edi. (M. Tven. Tom Saerning boshidan kechirganlari) The mighty river lay like an ocean at rest. (M. Twain. T. Sawyer) This work was translated from English to Uzbek, and the translator used lexical transformation of the translation during the translation process. That is, in English, the simile like an ocean at rest is literally translated as the ocean is resting (quiet), and in the translation it is as if it is asleep. He used the lexical transformation method of translation. We studied the similarities and differences between the Uzbek and English languages in a cross-linguistic comparative analysis of similes.

The fact that the official and scientific method does not have a linguistic-cultural and pragmalinguistic character is followed by norms such as using words in their meaning, adapting them to the text structure, not deviating from the stylistic requirements. However, the fact that affectivity in works of art is related to the human psyche makes it difficult to identify segmental units in a parallel corpus. In this case, it is somewhat difficult to find analogies in the search engine and to find an alternative in the second language. But this problem can be solved through linguistic units such as similes like... in English, -dek... in Uzbek. But these tools are not always evaluated as similes.

CONCLUSION. The use of transformations in the process of translation depends on whether the languages are typologically close or far from each other - on the level of their relatedness or non-relatedness. The translator determines which type of translation transformations to use. However, the translator himself does not think that I will use this particular translation transformation. He chooses translation transformations intuitively, based on his experience. Theoretically, translation transformations can be analyzed separately. In practice, in most cases, translation transformations come in mixed form. Pure and specific transformational constructions are widely used in the interpretation of untranslatable words, in the translation of specific words, and in the translation of stylistic methods that have a methodologically expressive character. Appropriate and effective application of translation transformations is a characteristic of experienced and skilled translators only. This does not mean that young translators do not have such an opportunity. Types of translation transformation are selected based on the typological, stylistic, linguostylistic, pragmatic, linguopragmatic, linguocultural, sociolinguistic, and linguotextological

characteristics of the two languages (original and translation) that came into contact with each other during translation. English, which belongs to the Germanic language family, is one of the world's most voluminous languages. It is the official language of the five largest countries of the world, Great Britain, USA, Canada, Australia and New Zealand. Most of the population of this country speaks English. According to scientists, the number of words in the English language is currently 1,494,010. According to the classification, this language belongs to inflectional languages. It is known that about 30 million people speak the Uzbek language in Uzbekistan, Afghanistan, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan, and Turkey. His vocabulary is from 120,000 to 220,000 words, according to different sources. According to its typological characteristics, the Uzbek language is considered an agglutinative language. In order to convert the texts written in the inflectional type into the agglutinative type text, where conversion is understood as translation, a number of translation transformations should be used.

Firstly, the vocabularies of the languages that have come into contact do not correspond to each other in terms of quantity, and secondly, the valency of forming word units, predictably, differs from each other. Grammatically speaking, the word structure and word groups of the two languages do not correspond to each other. In addition, the literal and figurative meaning of words, words with coloring, and special words (national words, reals) also differ in the two languages. These listed features require the use of phonetic, lexical, grammatical, lexical-grammatical, lexical-semantic and similar translation transformations in the translation process. In this translation, where there is a discrepancy in language units (phoneme, morpheme, word, phrase, sentence, and text), transformation is required. (Some scientists also include the text in the list of linguistic units. Their main argument is that just as a sentence is divided into a phrase, a phrase into a word, a word into a morpheme, and a morpheme into a phoneme, the text is also made up of sentences, phrases, words and similar units, so they recognize it as the largest linguistic unit. (However, this opinion is not supported by most scholars.) The most common and most used transformation is the change of word order. This type of transformation occurs at every step in the translation process. Among translation transformations, adding words, omitting words, summarizing, concretizing, copying, figurative translation methods are used as the basis for transformation in translation. A small number of transformations indicates that the languages are close to each other, and a large number of transformations indicates that the languages are far from each other.

REFERENCES.

1. Бархударов Л.С. Язык и перевод. - М.: Международные отношения, 1975. - 237 с.
2. Гарбовский Н.К. Переводческие трансформации и обучение переводу // Перевод как лингвистическая проблема. - М., 1982. - с. 13 - 22.
3. Латышев Л.К. Перевод; проблемы теории, практики и методики преподавания. - М.: Просвещение, 1988. - 160 с.
4. Латышев Л.К. О переводческих трансформациях // Методика и лингвистика. - М.: Наука, 1981.- 127- 138.
5. Тер-Минасова С.Г. Проблемы перевода: mission impossible? // Теория и практика перевода: Вестн. Моск. ун-та. Сер. 19. Лингвистика и межкультурная коммуникация. М.: Изд-во Московского ун-та, 2012. № 2. с. 9-18.
6. Рецкер Я.И. Теория перевода и переводческая практика: очерки лингвистической теории перевода. М.: Р. Валент, 2007. 244 с.
7. Комиссаров В.Н. Современное переводоведение. 2-е изд., испр. М.: Р.Валент, 2011. 408 с.
8. Гарбовский Н.К. Теория перевода: Учебник. М.: Изд-во Моск. Ун-та, 2007. 544 с.
9. Zokirova, N. (2022). МЕТАПОЗНАНИЕ И ФАКТОРЫ, ВЛИЯЮЩИЕ НА МЕТАКОГНИТИВНЫЕ СПОСОБНОСТИ В ПЕРЕВОДЕ . ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 22(22). извлечено от https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/8056
10. NS Zokirova. The Discursive Paradigm towards the Sociolinguistic Approach Pindus Journal of Culture, Literature, and ELT 2 (5), 207-211
11. Zokirova, N. S. (2022). Extralinguistic Features of Professional Discourse as Metalinguistic Nature of Special Communication. Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture, 3(6), 80-84. Retrieved from <https://cajipc.centralasianstudies.org/index.php/CAJLPC/article/view/383>
12. Xafizovna, R. N. . (2022). Linguistic Politeness Theory Review: Yueguo Gu, Sachiko Ide, Shoshena Blum Kulka, Bruce Frasher and William Nolen, Hornst Arndt and Richard Janney. Pindus Journal of Culture, Literature, and ELT, 2(5), 145–152
13. Ruziyeva Nilufar Xafizovna, & Axmedova Shahnoza Murodilloyevna. (2022). Interpretation of the Concepts of Linguoculturology. Eurasian Research Bulletin, 8, 36–38. Retrieved from <https://geniusjournals.org/index.php/erb/article/view/148>
14. Xafizovna , R. N. . (2023). The Study of Context: From Static to Dynamic. Miasto Przyszłości, 32, 242–246.